

Appendix A: Interview Guide

This is the interview guide for the semi-structured interviews. It is structured in main and follow-up questions and the numbering of the main questions resembles the order during the interview. Some questions were altered slightly for the external experts to have an industry focus instead of a specific company focus. These adaptations are indicated in square brackets. When required, we also asked context-specific spontaneous ad-hoc questions that are not included in the interview guide.

1. **Interviewee background:**
 - Current role and how long in that role?
 - Previous roles?
 - AI/ML proficiency? — How proficient would you consider yourself when it comes to AI and ML?
 - Regulatory requirements background?
 - Graduation year?
 - Educational background?
 - Start year at the current company?
2. **How are you adapting your current development practices for AI/ML systems?**
 - Do you have continuous engineering practices (aka pipelines) in place?
 - What is the release frequency or model update frequency of ML models in production?
3. **What comes to your mind when you think about the AI Act?**
4. **From your perspective, to what extent has the upcoming AI Act already been addressed within your organization[/ within the industry]?**
 - If yes, in what way?
 - Which departments have been involved in that so far?
 - As of now, what are the priorities at your company when it comes to the AI Act?
5. **High-risk AI Scenario — We now assume that one of your products would classify as a high-risk AI system and therefore needs to comply with the AI Act:**
 - *Answered per high-risk requirement:*
 - Which methods/approaches/techniques do you already have in place that could be mapped to the requirements?
 - For which requirements are you currently lacking solutions?
 - Which requirements do you consider most challenging to operationalize?
 - Where may external expertise be required?
6. **How big of a challenge do you think is compliance with the AI Act really?**
7. **How do you think the AI Act will impact your company[/ the industry]?**
 - What are the positive and negative side effects?
8. **Even if you don't plan on developing high-risk AI systems, which parts of the Act would you do anyway?**
 - What would bring the most value for you, if anything?
9. **Do you have anything more to add?**
10. **Is there anyone else you know who would be a suitable interview partner?**